

Tropospheric Propagation Modeling for Opportunistic Rain Sensing using Current and Future Broadcast and Broadband Satellites

Fabiola Sapienza⁽¹⁾, Giacomo Bacci⁽¹⁾, Filippo Giannetti⁽¹⁾, Attilio Vaccaro⁽²⁾, and Vincenzo Lottici⁽¹⁾

(1) Dipartimento Ingegneria dell'Informazione, University of Pisa, Pisa, Italy;

e-mail: {fabiola.sapienza, giacomo.bacci, filippo.giannetti, vincenzo.lottici}@ing.unipi.it

(2) MBI srl, Pisa, Italy; e-mail: avaccaro@mbigroup.it

Abstract

Opportunistic rain sensing using satellite broadband and broadcast channels has recently proven to be a very accurate, cost-effective, and broad-coverage technique. Since it relies on accurate propagation channel modeling, it needs to keep the pace with the evolution of satellite-based communication systems, in particular in terms of the ever-increasing range of radio frequencies foreseen for the integration with (beyond-)5G networks. This paper performs a performance comparison between: *i*) a consolidated, though overly simplified, tropospheric channel model which was devised by the ITU for the design of Ku-band satellite broadcasting links, and *ii*) a more elaborate one, featuring two layers and best suited to fit higher frequency links. Numerical results using data collected by a satellite terminal show that the second model provides better results, especially in the case of low rain rates.

1 Introduction

In 2017, satellite systems have gained momentum in the picture of state-of-the-art communication networks, thanks to the official introduction of non-terrestrial networks (NTNs) in Release 15 of the 3rd generation partnership project (3GPP) specifications for 5G standards [1]. Satellite technologies are already quite mature for backhauling and Internet of things (IoT). However, several gaps still exist [2], and since then a number of activities have been launched to fill such gaps and to consolidate the prominent role of satellite communications in the beyond-5G landscape.

This renovated interest has also been fueled by some ambitious private initiatives, such as SpaceX's Starlink, OneWeb and Amazon's Kuiper [3], which also boosted new technologies in related fields, such as launching and formation-flying techniques to support their mega-constellations. Hence, for broadband services we are witnessing the rise of a very articulated ecosystem of very high throughput satellites (VHTSS) operating at frequency ranges higher than the typical S-to-Ku bands. The same trend is also observed in TV broadcasting services, which are gradually migrating from Ku to Ka band and beyond.

To summarize, in the near future a very rich set of satellite constellations at any orbital radius, spanning from low earth orbit (LEO) to geosynchronous earth orbit (GEO) orbits, will be available. Such a scenario will significantly boost the potentiality of opportunistic approaches to rain sensing and estimation, especially for low-intensity precipitations, due to the increased sensitivity to rain effects of radio frequency (RF) propagation in the spectrum of millimeter waves and beyond. As is well known, precipitation monitoring is becoming of a paramount importance in many fields of applications, including: public safety, business-oriented services (e.g., agriculture), and personal services (e.g., leisure activities) [4]. Opportunistic satellite-based rain sensing turns out to be very appealing due to the following advantages [5]: *i*) no need for authorization, as satellite downlink (DL) signals can be freely acquired and processed; *ii*) easy installation of receiving terminals with minimal technical requirements; *iii*) scalability by deploying new terminals to obtain higher spatial density and *iv*) possibility to use inexpensive commercial-grade devices for domestic reception.

The application of dedicated algorithms relies on proper modeling of the propagation channel between the satellite and the on-ground receiver in the presence of rain. The most common method for estimating the long-term statistics of the slant-path rain-induced attenuation at a given location is the one provided by the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) as Recommendation ITU-R P.618-13 [6], which is largely used for link-budget calculations to determine the availability of a satellite service in a given location with respect to (wrt) atmospheric phenomena, and it is claimed to be valid for frequencies up to 55 GHz. The calculation described above requires: *i*) the specific attenuation model for rain, provided by Rec. ITU-R P.838-3 [7], whose coefficients are determined as functions of frequency, in the range from 1 to 1000 GHz; *ii*) the rain height, as given in Rec. ITU-R P.839-4 [8]. In this paper, we compare the performance accuracy of this model wrt the one proposed in [9], which is specifically tailored to the case of opportunistic satellite-based rain sensing, and that makes use of a refined characterization of the layers encountered by the RF signal when propagating through the troposphere.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Sect. 2 illustrates the fundamental concepts behind rain sensing techniques, whereas Sect. 3 presents the two propagation models considered in this work. Sect. 4 compares the experimental results obtained using real data with the two models, and Sect. 5 draws some conclusions and outlines future research directions.

2 Basics of satellite-based rain sensing

The opportunistic rain sensing method adopted in this study is based on measurements of microwave (μW) link attenuation. The overall attenuation A , introduced by the rain on the slanted *wet* path, can be evaluated from the measurements of the signal strength, which is directly provided by the receiving device itself. Most commercial receivers for satellite broadcasting provide in fact a measurement of the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) $\eta = E_s/N_0$, between the energy per symbol E_s and the one-sided power spectral density of the noise power spectral density (PSD) N_0 , so that the attenuation can be obtained as

$$A = (\eta^{\text{dry}}/\eta^{\text{wet}})(1 - \xi) + \xi \quad (1)$$

where the superscript *dry* denotes the reference level (suitably pre-stored during clear-sky days), the superscript *wet* denotes the current reading during precipitation, and ξ is a design parameter dependent on noise contributions (see eq. (4) in [9]). The value of the attenuation A to be put in (1) is derived by exploiting the popular power law [5]

$$A/L = \alpha \cdot R^\beta \quad (2)$$

where A in [dB] represents the total additional attenuation experienced by the signal strength level during the rain (wet condition) wrt the pre-rain value (dry condition); L in [km] is the length of the wet radio path; R in [mm/h] is the rain rate; and α and β are frequency- and polarization-dependent empirical coefficients, further detailed in the next section.

3 Analytical models for rain attenuation

3.1 ITU model

With reference to the geometrical model shown in Figure 1 for the analysis of satellite links during a rainy event, Rec. ITU-R P.839-4 [8] provides an internationally recognized model to evaluate the rain height, to be plugged into the method, outlined in Rec. ITU-R P.618.13 [6], for propagation prediction. This is a simple two-layer model made of: *i*) the *liquid layer* (LL), spanning from the ground level up to the rain height h_R , consisting of liquid uniform precipitation, and *ii*) the *ice layer* (IL), above h_R , i.e., a frozen precipitation layer where the hydrometeors are ice particles with low specific attenuation. According to [8], the mean annual rain height above mean sea level, h_R , can be obtained from the mean annual 0°C isotherm h_0 as:

$$h_R = h_0 + \Delta h, \quad (3)$$

Figure 1. Geometry of the satellite wet link (ITU model).

Figure 2. Geometry of the satellite wet link (two-layer tropospheric model).

where it is assumed to set $\Delta h = 360$ m. Let us remark that the additional term Δh yields a sort of *equivalent* rain height for the simplified model depicted in Figure 1, so as to take into account for the more complex layered structure of the real upper troposphere. According to the ITU-based model, the total attenuation experienced by the signal along the slanted wet path L (in the LL) between the satellite and the interactive satellite system (IST), and expressed by the power law in (2), can be calculated as

$$A = \alpha_{\text{LL}} \cdot R^{\beta_{\text{LL}}} \cdot \frac{h_0 + \Delta h}{\sin \theta}, \quad (4)$$

where: the coefficients α_{LL} and β_{LL} (in which the subscript LL stands for *liquid layer*) are determined as functions of the frequency and are provided in [7]; and θ is the satellite elevation angle, which is a known design parameter, depending on the ground receiver location and on the satellite longitude.

This simplified model shows some limitations, indeed, as it appears not to be flexible in the parameterization of the transition behavior in the upper layer, where ice particles coexist with raindrops. In particular, the effects of the frequency on the total attenuation experienced by the signal are included only in the pair of coefficients that characterize the propagation in the LL.

3.2 Two-layer tropospheric model

To evaluate the rain attenuation in a satellite link, we assume a stratiform precipitation, characterized by a clear

separation, at the 0°C isotherm height h_0 , between the upper layer, named the *ice particles layer*, made of frozen dry particles, and the lower layers in which the ice particles melt into raindrops. These lower layers are structured as follows: the superior one, named *melting layer (ML)*, which contains a combination of ice and rain; and the inferior, still named LL, which contains only rain. The geometry of the slanted satellite wet link through rain using the two-layer tropospheric model is shown in Figure 2. In the LL, the time-varying rainfall rate R is assumed to be independent of the vertical coordinate (i.e., constant along the path through the LL), while in the ML we assume that the liquid rain fraction varies linearly with height, passing from 0 at the h_0 to the full liquid rate R at the lower edge of the ML (for more details, see [9]).

According to (2), the overall attenuation introduced along the wet portion of the slanted path can be expressed as follows:

$$A = \left(\alpha_{LL} \cdot R^{\beta_{LL}} \cdot L_{LL} \right) + \Gamma(R) \cdot \left(\alpha_{ML} \cdot R^{\beta_{ML}} \cdot L_{ML} \right), \quad (5)$$

where: the subscripts LL and ML denote the parameters related to LL and ML, respectively; α_{LL} and β_{LL} can be obtained as per [7], as in Sect. 3.1; the coefficients

$$\alpha_{ML} = 9.7 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot f^2 + 2.0115 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot f - 0.1485, \quad (6)$$

$$\beta_{ML} = -6.9 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot f^2 + 5.014 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot f + 1.00915, \quad (7)$$

where f is the RF, are obtained through the interpolation of the specific attenuation, specifically computed in [10] for the ML in X- (9.35 GHz), Ka- (34.48 GHz), and W- (94 GHz) bands; the function

$$\Gamma(R) = \frac{1}{1 + (R/R_{ML})^\gamma} \quad (8)$$

is introduced to weigh the contribution of the ML attenuation, using $R_{ML} = 10 \text{ mm/h}$ as the maximum rain rate beyond which the ML effect can be considered to be negligible [11], and using a properly tuned exponent γ to control the smoothness of the transition; and the lengths L_{LL} and L_{ML} of the wet radio path in the two layers can be derived from simple considerations about the link geometry [5]:

$$L_{LL} = \frac{h_0 - \delta_{ML}}{\sin \theta}, \quad (9)$$

$$L_{ML} = \frac{\delta_{ML}}{\sin \theta \cdot (\beta_{ML} + 1)}, \quad (10)$$

where δ_{ML} measures the thickness of the ML, and its value is obtained experimentally. The 0°C isotherm height h_0 can be provided by either a short-term forecast based on weather models, or, more practically, it can be a fixed value based on daily or yearly averages taken at the receive location.

4 Experimental results

To evaluate the accuracy of the two models, we take advantage of a real-world experiment, using an IST to collect

Figure 3. Sample records of $\eta = E_s/N_0$ measured from the IST (left axis) and estimates of the rain rate (right axis).

Figure 4. Cumulated rain provided by the IST and the RG.

μW link quality measurements in terms of SNR η . The IST, installed in Massa, Tuscany (Italy), exploits a satellite link with the Eutelsat 10A satellite using the digital video broadcasting - satellite (version 2) (DVB-S2) format in Ku band ($f = 11,345.8 \text{ MHz}$). The blue line in Figure 3 depicts the SNR η (in dB, left axis) as a function of time, collected by the IST for a moderate rain event at the end of March 2022.

The rain rate (in mm/h, red lines and right axis) is computed using $h_0 = 2.6 \text{ km}$, based on yearly average values taken at the receive location, and a ML thickness $\delta_{ML} = 500 \text{ m}$. The solid line corresponds to the estimates obtained using the two-layer tropospheric model detailed in Sect. 3.2, whereas the dashed line reports the results using the ITU model described in Sect. 3.1.

Elaborating on these results, Figure 4 reports the cumulated rain (in mm) for the same event, using the same line style adopted in Figure 3. The reference ground truth rainfall data are obtained using a rain gauge (RG) of the Meteo Apuane network, located in the Massa center, which

provides cumulated rain measurements every 5 minutes. Such measurements are reported in Figure 4 using the black curve. As can be seen, the two-layer tropospheric model is in good agreement with the reference RG, whereas the ITU model provides over-estimates of the cumulated rain, due to the usage of a single layer that includes the compound effect of liquid and melting layers, without considering that the attenuation contribution introduced by the ML depends on the rainfall intensity.

For the sake of brevity, only a specific example is reported in this work. However, similar results can be obtained considering rain events with comparable intensity. For high rain rates, larger than 10mm/h, the two models provide coincident estimates, in accordance with [11], since the thickness of the ML reduces significantly.

5 Conclusions

In this paper we provide some results about the algorithm proposed in [9] to convert measurements of microwave satellite down-link into rainfall rate estimates, for two different tropospheric propagation models. In particular, this work proposes the usage of a two-layer tropospheric model for rain attenuation, valid for stratiform precipitations, which yields performance comparable to that of a traditional tipping-bucket RG, with the advantage of having a more flexible model compared to that proposed by the ITU. This novel tropospheric model offers, in fact, the flexibility to adapt its coefficients for both the LL and the ML to different frequency bands, unlike the simpler ITU model, which relies on a frequency-independent characterization of the effects of the upper layers.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the project INSIDERAIN funded by Tuscany regional administration (Italy), Decreto n. 21885, Dec. 18, 2020, by the project SCORE funded by European Commission's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101003534, and by the University of Pisa under "PRA - Progetti di Ricerca di Ateneo" (Institutional Research Grants) - Project no. PRA_2022_91 INTERCONNECT (Integrated communications, sensing and computing). The authors would like express their deepest gratitude to the partners of the project INSIDERAIN for the stimulating and fruitful technical discussions. This article is also based upon work from COST Action CA20136 OPENSENSE, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology).

References

[1] 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), "Study on New Radio (NR) to support non-terrestrial networks," 3GPP, Sophie Antipolis, France, Tech. Rep. 3GPP TR 38.811 V15.4.0, Oct. 2020.

[2] R. De Gaudenzi, M. Luise, and L. Sanguinetti, "The open challenge of integrating satellites into (beyond-) 5G cellular networks," *IEEE Network*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 168–174, Mar./Apr. 2022.

[3] O. B. Osoro and E. J. Oughton, "A techno-economic framework for satellite networks applied to low earth orbit constellations: Assessing Starlink, OneWeb and Kuiper," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 141 611–141 625, Oct. 2021.

[4] D. Kull, L. P. Riishojgaard, J. Eyre, and R. A. Varley, "The value of surface-based meteorological observation data," World Bank, Washington, DC, USA, Tech. Rep., 2021.

[5] F. Giannetti and R. Reggiannini, "Opportunistic rain rate estimation from measurements of satellite down-link attenuation: A survey," *Sensors*, 2021, vol. 21, no. 17, p. 5872, Aug. 2021.

[6] International Telecommunication Union (ITU) - R, "Propagation data and prediction methods required for the design of earth-space telecommunication systems," ITU-R, Geneva, Switzerland, Tech. Rep. Recommendation P.618-13, 2017.

[7] —, "Specific attenuation model for rain for use in prediction," ITU-R, Geneva, Switzerland, Tech. Rep. Recommendation P.838-3, 2005.

[8] —, "Rain height model for prediction methods," ITU-R, Geneva, Switzerland, Tech. Rep. Recommendation P.839-4, 2013.

[9] F. Giannetti, M. Moretti, R. Reggiannini, and A. Vaccaro, "The NEFOCAST system for detection and estimation of rainfall fields by the opportunistic use of broadcast satellite signals," *IEEE Aerosp. Electron. Syst. Mag*, vol. 34, no. 6, pp. 16–27, Jun. 2019.

[10] S. Y. Matrosov, "Assessment of radar signal attenuation caused by the melting hydrometeor layer," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 1039–1047, Apr. 2008.

[11] A. Dissanayake, J. Allnutt, and F. Haidara, "A prediction model that combines rain attenuation and other propagation impairments along earth-satellite paths," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 45, no. 10, pp. 1546–1558, Oct. 1997.